

EDGE MACHINING EFFECTS ON THE FAILURE OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITE COUPONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the effects of specimen cutting on off-axis tensile strengths of unidirectional composite materials. Results indicate that the cutting speed and the feed rate have great influence on the tensile strength of coupons. But this influence depends on the fibre orientations. A temperature analysis of cut surfaces after the passage of the tool does not allow to draw any conclusion. Only optical observations show delaminations, which represent possible crack initiations, but subsurface damage needs to be assessed more thoroughly.

KEYWORDS: HIGH SPEED MILLING, CUTTING DAMAGE, COMPOSITE MATERIALS, OFF-AXIS TENSION

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are more and more used for structural parts which are subjected to important mechanical stresses. Thus, it is necessary to know perfectly the mechanical characteristics (elastic moduli, ultimate strengths) of these materials. They are commonly derived from mechanical tests performed on composite coupons. Nevertheless, their preparation is often achieved by machining, in particular by edge milling. The composite testing standards remain vague on the conditions of coupon preparation and related damage tolerance. For example, in NF EN ISO 2818 standard [1], which concerns only mechanical testing of polymers, it is prescribed that: "machined surfaces and edges of finished coupons should be exempt from visible cracks, scratches or any other defects when they are observed by means of a low magnification lens (x5)". When looking at a specific composite testing standard, such as ASTM D3039 [2] (Standard test method for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials) or ASTM D5379 [3] (Standard Test Method for shear properties of composite materials by the V-Notched beam method), it is stated that "the specimens may be molded individually to avoid edge and cutting effects or they may be cut from plates after bonding on tab materials. If they are cut from plates, precautions must be taken to avoid notches, undercuts, or rough or uneven surfaces". The previous version of this standard indicates that when machined, a specimen should be saw cut at least 3 mm (1/8 in) oversize and final dimensions obtained by milling or grinding, or both, with water flow. Many studies have been carried out to investigate the relation between cutting conditions and state of machined surfaces of composite materials. Surface finish, respect of tolerances and tool life are usually considered. Nevertheless, Tagliaferri et al. [4] have studied the influence of drilling parameters on the machined finish and mechanical properties of glass fibre-reinforced plastics. They have found that the tensile strength of a composite specimen with a drilled hole is not influenced by drilling-induced damage while bearing strength recorded significant decrease with growing degree of damage. Moreover, the authors clearly addressed that the ratio between the revolution speed and the thrust speed of the drill is the most significant parameter that affects the bearing strength. Persson et al. [5] have studied the effects of hole drilling on static and fatigue mechanical performance of composite laminates. They discovered that the use of PCD tools when drilling carbon/epoxy laminates reduced the static bearing strength by about 10% compared to values obtained by the use of a dagger drill (cemented carbide drill with a very sharp tip angle) or a

diamond grain coated mandrel in a routing configuration (orbital drilling). Kitano et al. [6], in a study of edge finishing effects on transverse cracking of cross-ply CFRP laminates, indicated that the edge finish conditions of composite coupons must be carefully considered in analysis or comparison of available transverse cracking data. In their study, the incidence of the specimen preparation on the onset of transverse cracking and crack density is emphasized, but no significant effect on the ultimate tensile strain was recorded. Arola and Ramulu [7] studied the flexural properties of graphite/epoxy specimens machined by three methods (the abrasive waterjet, circular diamond saw and shaper planer mounted with PCD inserts). Although the textures of the machined surface were different from one process to the others, no significant differences in strength have been noted under bending loads. But these results are not surprising. Indeed, in their loading configuration, the micro-cracks are initiated mainly on the unmachined surfaces. Finally, Guégan [8] tested glass/epoxy tensile specimens prepared with two different tools. He noted a decrease of 8.8% on the ultimate tensile stress when the milling tool is switched from PCD to diamond coated. In cyclic 4-pt bending of open hole composite coupons, Guégan showed the importance of thermal damage on the mechanical performance and the weak effect of the delamination damage but was not able to relate such effects to surface roughness. Wang et al. [9] noticed the same phenomena in orthogonal cutting of graphite/epoxy composites. The degree of matrix smearing on the machined surface increased with increasing fibre orientation and served to reduce the surface roughness.

In conclusion:

- because of their inhomogeneous and anisotropic properties, the cut surface damages have significant effects on mechanical performances of composites coupons;
- surface roughness does not seem an appropriate damage indicator to characterise the mechanical behaviour of composite materials;
- cutting conditions affect damage and mechanical performances;
- cutting damage will not systematically influence the mechanical behaviour of composite specimens. If fracture takes place far from the cut surfaces or if it is initiated in a compression mode (crack closure), the cutting effects are insignificant.

These conclusions suggest the need for additional work, particularly to investigate other mechanical tests potentially prone to machining-induced damage. Thus the choice of the test in this study (off-axis tensile test) is motivated by his potential susceptibility to machining-induced damage.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The off-axis tension specimens have been extracted from E-glass/epoxy continuous unidirectional panels. The composite panels have been made from prepregs referenced Vicotex® BEM10/29.58%/25x2400-60mm. The fibre volume fraction is approximately 46%. The nominal thickness of the plates is 2.3mm. Its mechanical characteristics have been measured with tensile tests according to standard ASTM D 3039 [2] and in shear by standard ASTM D 5379 [3]. The results are $E_{xx} = 23.3$ GPa, $E_{yy} = 6.5$ GPa, $G_{xy} = 4.4$ GPa and $\nu_{xy} = 0.32$. The off-axis tensile test configuration for this study is described in figure 1. Three fibre orientations θ of the coupons have been selected for this study: 15°, 30° and 45°. Oblique end-tabs have been used to generate a homogeneous stress field into the coupon [10], [11]. The dimensions of the coupons are indicated in table 1.

Figure 1: off-axis tensile test with oblique end-tabs.

Fibre orientation (°)	Width (mm)	Length (mm)	Tab angle (°)
15	14	200	61
30	20	200	55
45	25	180	61

Table 1: specimens dimensions

The preparation of the tensile specimens included two phases:

- cutting of flat strips from the panel using a diamond saw. The specimens are 6 mm wider than the finished dimensions;
- milling-finish of 3 mm on each side to adjust the coupons width to the final dimensions. Two two-flute milling tools were selected:
- sintered carbide tool of manufacturer Albert Denis and supplied under reference 5275 RW STG 56, 8 mm in diameter (figure 2(a)),
- PCD insert of manufacturer DIXI and commercialised under reference DIXI 2030, 10 mm in diameter (figure 2(b)).

The cutting parameters (table 2) have been determined from the bibliography [12] and the technical documents from the manufacturers.

a: carbide tool.

b: PCD tool.

Figure 2: Milling tools.

Tool reference	Cutting speed V_c m.min ⁻¹		Feed rate f_z mm.tooth ⁻¹ .rev ⁻¹		Rotation speed rev.min ⁻¹		Feed rate V_f mm.min ⁻¹	
	mini	maxi	mini	maxi	mini	maxi	mini	maxi
carbide	100	450	0.03	0.15	3980	17900	239	5370
PCD	100	1000	0.03	0.15	3180	31800	191	9540

Table 2: Cutting conditions

In the second time, and only for PCD tool and fibre orientations of 15° and 45°, four other cutting configurations have been selected to complete the previous experimental study:

- $V_f=400$ mm.min⁻¹ ; $V_c=209$ m.min⁻¹
- $V_f=2500$ mm.min⁻¹ ; $V_c=393$ m.min⁻¹
- $V_f=5800$ mm.min⁻¹ ; $V_c=1302$ m.min⁻¹
- $V_f=11000$ mm.min⁻¹ ; $V_c=1152$ m.min⁻¹

It should be reminded that:

- the cutting speed V_c corresponds to the tool peripheral speed in the composite material. In our case, $V_c = \pi DN/1000$, where V_c is the cutting speed in m.min⁻¹, D the tool diameter in mm and N the tool rotation speed in rev.min⁻¹.

- the feed rate V_f corresponds to the tool speed in the material, and therefore $V_f = N.Z.f_z$, where Z is the number of tool teeth and f_z the tooth feed in the material in $\text{mm.tooth}^{-1}.\text{rev}^{-1}$.

As can be seen in previous work ([9], for instance), the chip formation depends on the fibre orientation with respect to the cutting direction. In this study, all coupons are machined as described in figure 3.

Figure 3: Milling configuration

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The specimens have been tested to failure with a constant loading rate of $1 \text{ mm}.\text{min}^{-1}$. The results are the averages of 5 tests for each configuration, with error bars representing \pm two standard deviation. For the 15° fibre orientation, as can be seen on figure 4, the off-axis strength is not influenced by the type of tool (PCD or tungsten carbide). It is important to note here that the wear of the carbide tools was insignificant. On the other hand, a significant decrease of the tensile failure stress can be noted for a high cutting speed associated to a high feed rate. For this fibre orientation (15°) and this tooth feed ($0.15 \text{ mm}.\text{min}^{-1}.\text{rev}^{-1}$), the decrease in failure stress is about 28% for the carbide tool when the cutting speed increases from $100 \text{ m}.\text{min}^{-1}$ to $450 \text{ m}.\text{min}^{-1}$, and about 29% for the PCD tool when the cutting speed increases from $100 \text{ m}.\text{min}^{-1}$ to $1000 \text{ m}.\text{min}^{-1}$.

Figure 4: Fibre orientation 15° . Error bar: ± 2 standard deviation

Nevertheless, this phenomenon was not noted for the 30° orientation. (figure 5). In this case, the scatter of the off-axis tension results is more important and does not consequently allow to conclude.

Finally, in the case of the 45° orientation, the tendency noticed for 15° is inverted (figure 6). Using a small tooth feed tends to decrease the off-axis strengths. The reduction in failure stress is 32% for a cutting speed of 100 m.min⁻¹ and the tungsten carbide tool when the tooth feed decreases from 0.15

Figure 5: Fibre orientation 30°. Error bar: ± 2 standard deviation

Figure 6: Fibre orientation 45°. Error bar: ± 2 standard deviation

mm.tooth⁻¹.rev⁻¹ to 0.03 mm.tooth⁻¹.rev⁻¹ and 46% with the PCD tool for the same reduction of tooth feed. On the other hand, this effect vanishes for high cutting speeds, although scatter tends to increase. The off-axis tensile failure stresses reach a lower level than those noticed for low speeds and high feed rates, with the carbide tool as well as with the PCD tool. One of the possible reasons of these variations of mechanical behaviour could be thermal damage. Measurements of the maximum temperature of the milled surfaces have been performed using an infrared camera (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Maximum temperatures on cut surfaces. Error bar: ± 2 standard deviation

Milled surface temperatures are lower than the glass transition temperature, which is about 145°C for this M10 epoxy resin, except for the 30° orientation and the carbide tool. It is not surprising that carbide tools give rise to higher temperatures than PCD tools because of the enhanced cutting edge sharpness for the latter. Nevertheless, it is clear that thermal damage cannot account for the mechanical variations observed previously.

One other possible reason of the variations of mechanical behaviour could be physical damage. Optical observations of cut surfaces were performed using an optical microscope (see figure 8) The

cut surface damage is dependent on cutting conditions, cutting speed V_c and feed rate V_f . Naturally, the influence of the fibre orientation is also important. From these images, a damage parameter has been derived by image analysis as the ratio between damaged and undamaged surface. The results confirm the dependence of the percentage of damaged surface on the ratio V_f / V_c (feed rate to cutting speed), as can be seen in figure 9(a). Physically, this ratio corresponds to the maximum chip thickness divided by tool diameter, and is proportional to f_z . But this parameter does not seem correlate exactly with the off-axis tensile failure stress (figure 9(b)). Several configurations of cutting parameters V_f and V_c can have the same ratio V_f / V_c . For example (figure 9(b), fibre orientation 15°), for the same ratio $V_f / V_c = 0.00955$, the off-axis tensile failure stress of the coupons machined at $V_c = 100 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and $V_f = 955 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ ($f_z = 0.15 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{tooth}^{-1}\cdot\text{rev}^{-1}$) is 224.8 MPa, whereas that cut with $V_c = 1000 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and $V_f = 9550 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ ($f_z = 0.15 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{tooth}^{-1}\cdot\text{rev}^{-1}$) is 159.5 Mpa.

Figure 8: Optical observations of cut surfaces

Figure 9: Analysis versus ratio V_f / V_c

The $f_z \cdot V_c$ parameter seems more representative of the mechanical performances (figure 10(b)). This parameter is proportional to the rate of chip volume (and also proportional to V_f). But unless the V_f/V_c ratio, $f_z \cdot V_c$ does not well represent cut surface damage. This difficulty in determining a reliable parameter characterizing the mechanical behaviour and the cut surface damage suggests that other sources of damage are influential. In particular, subsurface damage, difficult to detect and quantify with surface observations, may play an important role. This point still remains under investigation.

Figure 10: Analysis versus ratio $f_z \cdot V_c$

CONCLUSION

This experimental study shows the complexity of the cut surface damage of composite materials. The main conclusions are:

- If tool wear is avoided, there is no significant difference of mechanical performances between coupons milled by carbide tool and those milled by PCD tool.
- For the 15° fibre orientation, the mechanical performance decreases with high cutting speed associated to high feed rates.
- For the 45° fibre orientation, the best mechanical performance is obtained using a small cutting speed and a high feed rate.
- The V_f/V_c ratio (feed rate to cutting speed) characterizes the cut surface damage, but the $f_z \cdot V_c$ parameter seems more representative of the mechanical performances.
- More investigations are necessary to better characterize the cut surface damages. In particular, subsurface damage should be observed and evaluated.

REFERENCES

- [1] AFNOR. Plastiques : "Préparation des éprouvettes par usinage". European Standard, 1997.
- [2] ASTM D 3039/D 3039M. "Standard test method for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials", 2000.
- [3] ASTM D 5379/D 5379M. "Standard test method for shear properties of composites materials by the v-notched beam method", 1998.
- [4] V. Tagliaferri, G. Caprino, and A. Diterlizzi. "Effect of drilling parameters on the finish and mechanical properties of GFRP composites". *International Journal of Machine Tools & Manufacture*, 30(1), pp.77-84, 1990.
- [5] E. Persson, I. Eriksson, and L. Zackrisson. "Effects of hole machining defects on strength and fatigue life of composites laminates". *Composites: Part A*, 28, pp.141-151, 1997.

- [6] A. Kitano, K. Yoshioka, K. Noguchi, and J. Matsui. "Edge finishing effects on tranverse cracking of cross-ply CFRP laminates". In Antonio Miravete, editor, *ICCM 9*, volume 5, pages 169-176, 1993.
- [7] D. Arola and M. Ramulu. "Machining-induced surface texture effects on the flexural properties of a graphite/epoxy laminate". *Composites*, 25(8), pp. 822-834, 1994.
- [8] P. Guegan. "Contribution à la qualification de l'usinage de matériaux composites à matrice organique" (Contribution to the assessment of the machining of polymer matrix composites). *PhD thesis*, University of Nantes, 1994.
- [9] D.H. Wang, M. Ramulu, and D. Arola. "Orthogonal cutting mechanisms of graphite/epoxy. Part 1: Unidirectional laminate". *International Journal of Machine Tools & Manufacturing*, 35(12), pp. 1623-1638, 1995.
- [10] C.T. Sun and I. Chung. "An oblique end-tab design for testing off-axis composite specimens". *Composites*, 24, pp. 619-623, 1993.
- [11] F. Pierron, E. Alloba, Y. Surrel, and A. Vautrin. "Whole-field assessment off the effects of boundary conditions on the strain field in off-axis tensile testing of unidirectional composites". *Composites Science and Technology*, 58, pp. 1939-1947, 1998.
- [12] H. Schulz. "Fraisage grande vitesse des matériaux métalliques et non métalliques", chapter 4.7, pp.175-201. Sofetec, 1997.